

**COEXISTING WITH THE SEMIARID
AND STRENGTHENING
FAMILY FARMING**

2025

The PDHC is named after the **Catholic Bishop of Ceará, Dom Hélder Câmara**, who died in 1999 at the age of 90. Dom Hélder Câmara became known worldwide as an important political and religious leader in the history of Brazil, for his commitment to social justice and his fight in defense of human rights. The priest dedicated his life to charitable work with the poor and marginalized against hunger and misery, as well as the search for social transformation, showing genuine faith and hope in Brazilian youth to bring about this transformation.

“The only legitimate war is the one against misery and ignorance”.

Dom Hélder Câmara

Dom Hélder Câmara Project: coexisting with the semiarid and strengthening family farming

PRESIDENCY OF THE FEDERATIVE REPUBLIC OF BRAZIL PRESIDENT

Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva

VICE-PRESIDENT

Geraldo José Rodrigues Alckmin Filho

MINISTRY OF AGRARIAN DEVELOPMENT AND FAMILY AGRICULTURE MINISTRY

Luiz Paulo Teixeira Ferreira

EXECUTIVE SECRETARY OF THE MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT AND FAMILY FARMING

Fernanda Machiaveli Morão de Oliveira

SECRETARY FOR LAND GOVERNANCE, TERRITORIAL AND SOCIO- ENVIRONMENTAL DEVELOPMENT

Moisés Savian

Prepared by

Secretariat for Land Governance, Territorial and Socio-Environmental
Development (SFDT/MDA)

Department of Evaluation, Monitoring, Studies and Strategic Information
(DAMEI/MDA)

Institute of Public Policy and Sustainable Development (IPPDS/UFV)

Organization

Ana Carolina Cançado Teixeira

Lucas Schumacker Maluf

Rosimere Miranda Fortini
Sheyla Gomes de Almeida

Layout and editing

Adriana Freitas

Illustration and cover

Luciana Fernandes

Maps:

Laís Rosa Oliveira

Proofreading

Cynthia Maritz dos Santos Ferraz Machado

Photos

Acervo PDHC/MDA

PROJETO
DOM
HÉLDER
CÂMARA

Contents

Acronyms and abbreviations	7	ATER in the PDHC II	33
Preface	9	Other PDHC II actions and partnerships	35
Project's general objective	10	Impacts of PDHC II	40
PDHC phases	11	Rural women	44
		Rural youth	46
		Traditional peoples and communities	47
Dom Hélder Câmara Project I	12		
Area of operation	13		
PDHC I objectives	14	Dom Hélder Câmara Project III	49
PDHC I BUDGET	15	Background	50
ATER: one of the centrepieces of the		PDHC III components and Corresponding	
PDHC I actions	16	actions	51
Other PDHC I actions	18	Alignment of PDHC III with the sustainable	
Impacts of PDHC I	20	development goals	54
Partnerships within PDHC I	24	Focus of actions and the budget for PDHC III	55
Testimonials about PDHC I	26	Territorial approach and area of operation	56
		Target audience and access to the project	57
Dom Hélder Câmara Project II	29		
Area of operation	30		
PDHC II objective	31		
PDHC II budget	32		

Acronyms and abbreviations

AECID – Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation
ANATER – National Agency for Technical Assistance and Rural Extension
ATER – Technical Assistance and Rural Extension
ATV – Virtual Technical Assistance
AWPB – Annual Work Plan and Budgeting
CAATINGA – Center for Assistance and Support for Workers and Alternative Non-Governmental Institutions
CadÚnico – Unified Registry for Social Programs
CEFFAS – Family Centers for Alternance Training
CIRAD – French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development
CODEVASF – Development Company of the São Francisco and Parnaíba Valleys
CONDEL – Advisory Board
CRQ – Quilombo Remnant Communities
CSST– South-South and Triangular Cooperation
DU – Demonstration Units
EaD – Distance Education
EMBRAPA – Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation
ESPLAR – Rural Planning and Advisory Office
FETARN – Federation of Agricultural Workers of the State of Rio Grande do Norte
FINEP – Funding Authority for Studies and Projects
FISP – Social and Productive Investment Financing
FNDCT – National Fund for Scientific and Technological Development
GEF – Global Environment Facility
IF Sertão – Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Sertão Pernambucano
IFAD – International Fund for Agricultural Development

INCRA – National Institute for Colonization and Agrarian Reform
INSA – Instituto Nacional do Semiárido
KM – Knowledge Management
M&E – Monitoring and Evaluation
MCTI – Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation
MDA – Ministry of Agrarian Development and Family Agriculture
MDS – Ministry of Social Development and Fight Against Hunger
MEC – Ministry of Education
MMTR-NE – Movement of Female Rural Workers from the Northeast
NGOs – Non-Governmental Organizations
PAA – Food Acquisition Program
PCT – Traditional Peoples and Communities
PDHC – Dom Hélder Câmara Project
PMU – Project Management Unit
PRONAF – National Program for the Strengthening of Family Farming
RU – Reference Units
SARA – Environmental Sanitation and Water Reuse
SDG – Sustainable Development Goals
SFDT – Secretariat for Land Governance, Territorial and Socio-Environmental Development
SUDENE – Superintendence for the Development of Brazilian Northeast
TEDs – Decentralized Execution Terms
UFCG – Federal University of Campina Grande
UFRN – Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte
UFV – Federal University of Viçosa
UN – United Nations
UNB – University of Brasília

Preface

The Dom Hélder Câmara Project (PDHC) started operating in the early 2000s as a result of a series of popular demands in the semiarid region of Brazil to address the pressing problems historically experienced by the population. It was conceived as a pilot experience for a strategic project within the set of public actions of the then Ministry of Agrarian Development (MDA), which could generate and disseminate references to guide public policies for the sustainable rural development of family farming in the semiarid region.

By valuing local and territorial identity, recognizing and integrating the knowledge and practices of family farmers in the semiarid region, technological innovations and processes of co-construction of knowledge were implemented, with the central axis of Technical Assistance and Rural Extension (ATER) articulating the socio-political, environmental, cultural, economic, technological, gender and generational dimensions.

Coordinated by the Ministry of Agrarian Development and Family Agriculture (MDA) and co-financed by the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), the PDHC has established itself as a benchmark for actions aimed at reducing poverty and inequalities among rural populations in the Brazilian semiarid region, based on the principles of agroecology and coexistence with the semiarid, as well as a methodological benchmark and articulation of partnerships for MDA public policies and actions. In 2025, the PDHC will celebrate its 25th anniversary and enter its third phase. In addition to continuing to contribute to rural poverty reduction, PDHC III will emphasize actions to address nutrition and food insecurity in family farming, the impacts of climate change in the semiarid region, and gender, generational, and ethnic/racial inequalities. To this end, the MDA will work to ensure that family farmers in the rural areas covered by the project have access to public policies, technological innovations, and resources that promote sustainable, biodiverse, and climate-resilient food systems.

This booklet aims to provide a brief record of this trajectory, highlighting the PDHC as a relevant public action in tackling socio-environmental issues experienced by people living in the semiarid region of Brazil, as well as its fundamental role in promoting sustainable rural development and solidarity.

The Dom Hélder Câmara Project team.

Project's general objective

The Project operates in the semi-arid region of Brazil and its goal is to contribute to

REDUCE:

- *rural poverty;*
- *nutrition and food insecurity; and*
- *gender, generation and ethnic-racial inequalities.*

To this end, it aims to **FACILITATE THE ACCESS TO:**

- *public policies;*
- *technological innovations; and*
- *resources that promote sustainable, biodiverse and climate-resilient food systems.*

PDHC phases

The PDHC was established in 2000 by the MDA in partnership with IFAD and was implemented in two phases with specific implementation measures. With a 25-year history, the PDHC has become a benchmark for projects that promote sustainable rural development and poverty reduction in Brazil.

The third phase is already a reality and is expected to last six years!

★ PDHC IN THE TOP-5! ★

In 2024, the PDHC was internationally recognized as an example of a project that is effectively transforming thousands of people and positively impacting family farming in the semi-arid region of Brazil. As a result, the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) has ranked the project in the top-5 of its most successful operations worldwide!

A faint, light green line-art illustration of a diverse group of people, including men, women, and children, standing together in a community setting. The background is a solid dark green color.

Dom Hélder Câmara Project I¹

¹ The information and data included in this section comes from the PDHC I Completion Report.

Area of operation

The PDHC I started operating in 2000 with the aim of improving the social and economic conditions of participating subjects of the Brazilian agrarian reform program and family farmers located in the semiarid of the Northeast region.

It operated in eight areas in six states of the Northeast regio: Ceará, Paraíba, Rio Grande do Norte, Pernambuco, Sergipe and Piauí.

PDHC I objectives:

General and specifics

Initially, the main objective of PDHC I was to improve the socio-economic conditions of rural families from the semiarid of the Northeast region, through the access to markets and improvements in the management of production activities.

However, there was a consensus that it was necessary to adjust the general objective of PDHC I to something broader and so it was re-defined as:

Generate and disseminate references that can guide public policies to combat poverty and support sustainable rural development in the semiarid region.

The specific objectives were to:

increase water and food security;

expand technological and management capacity;

increase productive occupation, employment and income;

support the diversification of activities and crops;

expand access to financial services and credit; and

support democratic inter-institutional spaces for the participatory implementation of public policies.

PDHC I BUDGET

In order to achieve the objectives proposed in PDHC I, a total of

BRL 182,892,000.00

was invested, including direct and indirect resources.

Of this total:

62%

Federal government budget through loan agreement with IFAD

38%

Co-financing through partnerships and access to public policies

Ater: one of the centrepieces of the PDHC I actions

The provision of technical assistance was one of the central axes of PDHC I and had a direct impact in the rural community by enabling:

16

water security and changes in production that have led to improved food security and the availability of surpluses for sale, as well as added value in commercialized products and access to markets; and

access to public policies and social technologies.

The provision of ATER services within PDHC I was carried out by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) working under the guidelines and rules set out in the Terms of Reference prepared by the Project Management Unit (PMU). Thus, in PDHC I, ATER services were provided to a total of

15,050

families from rural communities and agrarian reform settlements.

Other PDHC I actions

Although ATER services were present in most of PDHC I interventions, other equally important actions were part of the Project's set of activities. Thus, in the first phase of PDHC:

11,727

Families have benefited from Social and Productive Investment Financing (FISP) projects, generally aimed at:

- food security and income generation;
- water security;
- basic sanitation;
- community infrastructure; and
- agricultural production.

4,520

people, including youths and adults, have become literate. The literacy initiative has had a positive impact on the lives of these people by raising their self-esteem and interest in participating in decision-making processes, as well as providing them with a greater capacity to learn and take advantage of ATER services. In addition, highly effective content and methods were implemented in these actions. To this end, the educators underwent prior training to be able to conduct the courses for the participating subjects.

Still with regard to PDHC I actions, the cross-cutting actions in gender, generation and ethnicity stand out. Their aim was to:

•ensure equal participation of men and women in the different actions of the Project;

• strengthening the role of young people; and

•guide actions to support quilombola communities.

In general, these cross-cutting actions were implemented by NGOs called 'reference' partners in each territory. The reference partners were responsible for training both ATER technicians and social mobilisers, as well as the participating subjects.

Cross-cutting actions include:

The preparation of gender diagnostics in the territories of Pajeú, Apodi, Cariri, Sertão Central de Ceará and Sertão Sergipano, as well as generational diagnostics to guide cross-cutting actions in the different components of the project.

The development of a campaign to issue documents to rural women in the territories of Pajeú, Apodi, Cariri, Sertão Central de Ceará and Sertão Sergipano. This action enabled 14,257 women to obtain their documents.

The support for the development of communication and cultural activities (such as setting up a community radio and publishing a newspaper) by young people in the territories of Apodi and Sertão Central, in the state of Ceará.

The training of "rights multipliers" on issues related to women's and Young people's rights, such as combating violence against women, citizenship and women's rights, and access to credit.

The monitoring of the management of demonstration units and FISP projects of women's and youth by the reference partners.

The promotion of training, exchanges and workshops on ethnic and cultural themes in quilombola communities in the territory of Pajeú.

The establishment of Working Groups on Credit, gender and Generation in the territories of Pajeú, Cariri, Apodi Sertão Sergipano and São João de Piauí to promote spaces for discussion on the credit lines of PRONAF Mulher and PRONAF Jovem.

Impacts of PDHC I

Based on the results of the impact evaluation, carried out with a sample of participating families, it was observed that, with the Project:

20

in relation to agricultural practices, with the Project:

With regard to animal husbandry:

Still, according to the PDHC I impact evaluation:

of the participating families who took part in the survey informed that there had been changes in their eating habits, as well as:

- diversification of agricultural production; and
- increased meat and milk production.

Among the participating families who had made changes to their production methods, there was an increase in their income of:

1 to 1.5
minimum wages.

In addition, PDHC I generated positive impacts on:

Capacity building assets

- development of new knowledge and skills in productive, technological and marketing aspects acquired by farmers; and
- new knowledge acquired by local professionals and technicians.

Social assets and autonomy

- training of new leaders;
- increased self-esteem;
- changes in attitudes and greater autonomy for women; and
- strengthening the ability to identify and solve problems.

542 rural libraries

were implemented in the eight territories where the Project operates. This enabled access to books and encouraged reading, as well as supporting formal and non-formal education in rural communities.

Institutions and services

- creation of a group of ATER service providers suited to the demands of family farmers;
- strengthening organizations representing rural workers and settlers;
- establishment of financial institutions to provide microcredit; and
- strengthening local spaces for discussion and deliberation.

Caring for the environment

- changes in production by adopting sustainable production practices;
- greater use of biological and organic inputs;
- application of sustainable methods for the management of natural resources; and
- introduction of water storage methods.

Financial assets

- access to credit: 7,200 families had access, for the first time, to resources from the National Program for the Strengthening of Family Farming (PRONAF); and
- new sources of income.

Access to markets

- creation and strengthening of agro-ecological fairs located in the municipalities, where farmers could sell their products directly; and
- commercialization of products via governmental purchasing programs, such as the Food Acquisition Program (PAA).

Partnerships within PDHC I

All the actions carried out under PHDC I were made possible by the support of a committed network of partners composed of:

Still with Regard to the Project's partners, the PDHC I also formalized partnerships that supported cross-cutting actions focused on promoting gender equality. Reference partners included:

- Casa da Mulher do Nordeste, territory of Pajeú (Pernambuco);
- CAATINGA, Sertão do Araripe (Pernambuco);
- Centro Feminista 8 de Março, Apodi (Rio Grande do Norte);
- ESPLAR, Sertão Central (Ceará);
- Cunhã and Centro da Mulher 8 de Março, Sertão do Cariri (Paraíba); and
- ONG Grupo Mulher Maravilha, territory of Pajeú (Pernambuco).

Testimonials about PDHC I

Edvânia de Souza Silva (53)

is an agronomist with a degree in Agricultural Sciences and a specialization in Family Farming and Rural Education. She worked at PDHC I and her duties were related to direct technical assistance to communities and settlements, with a frequency of two technical visits per week. Her tasks included: designing production projects; developing action plans with the project's participating subjects; conducting quarterly evaluations; preparing the annual work plan and budgeting (AWPB); implementing FISP projects for free range chicken, goat, pig, fish and mandala systems; and preparing DUs for fodder fields and sweet palm, among others. Regarding the lessons learned, Edvânia says that:

"I have learned a lot as a professional working with our farmers, with the weekly planning and monitoring, with the implementation of the productive projects and the follow-up. I've learned a lot about the environment, agroecology, gender relations, solidarity economy and productive backyards".

Givanilson Porfirio da Silva (49)

worked in the technical coordination of social mobilization in PDHC I between 2003 and 2010 in the territories of Sertão do Pajeú and Sertão do Araripe (both in Pernambuco). Regarding the way in which the rural technical assistance actions were implemented with the families, Givanilson pointed out that:

"This implementation model generates a high level of commitment to the goals, because they are real demands, built by the families themselves, based on a strategic view of their reality, and not made for them in Brasília or on a general call for action, which may be important, but is not rooted in their real and fundamental demands. That's why the implementation was almost 100% each year.

The families themselves and the social mobilization monitored the implementation of the ATER Action Plan, and partial reports were also presented at the Territorial Committee meetings to see the percentage of implementation and the difficulties encountered, in order to find a solution. This model of interaction generated a lot of co-responsibility. The social mobilization was monitored by the families, who presented an evaluation report. The participation of everyone in the definition of the goals, in the territory itself, was the great element of identity and commitment to them, because it generated a sense of belonging and dialogue for their construction".

Testimony from Maria Auxiliadora Dias Cabral (75),

who lives in a rural community in the municipality of São José do Belmonte, Pernambuco:

“ My name is Maria Auxiliadora Dias Cabral, I'm 75 years old, a farmer and popular feminist educator with a degree in history, a single mother of a daughter and two grandchildren. I have always been a rural feminist, working to reduce gender inequalities, and I have always been an activist, participating in movements and organizations related to the countryside.

As part of the overall coordination of the “No Rural Worker Without a Document” campaign, it was a unique experience for me. In addition to contributing to the documentation of rural women workers, this project offered direct training for 45 communities in the Northeast region, reaching 125 groups per community, with an average of eight women in each group. This amounts to approximately 1,000 women leaders directly trained in themes like citizenship, gender, rural women's identity and public policy. Approximately 70% of the grassroots rural women's groups were included in the PDHC I training processes.

This campaign was a historic milestone, to the point of being nationally recognized and becoming a public policy that is now a responsibility of the Government. Today, everyone in the rural and urban areas, regardless of gender or race, has the right to obtain their documents free of charge. This makes the right to citizenship accessible, because we are all equal. Having a document is a matter of citizenship!

In general, despite the difficulties, the work has been successful, not least because the focus has been on educating and documenting women's citizenship throughout the northeast. As a result, women now have access to various benefits, including social security. The PDHC brought about progress that is still evident in the eyes of all the participants, including the women who, like me, served as leaders. We all learned a lot from the PDHC, but we also taught. The movement's practice is still recognized today as a multiplier of leadership cadres, groups of theories and knowledge.

It was noticeable that after the PDHC support, there was greater visibility for the organizations implementing the project, as well as for the MMTR-NE leaders who were already working in their bases but didn't have the resources to conduct the training. In addition, the PDHC opened doors to more partnerships through the implementation of other Movement projects with international cooperation agencies.

We have had many visible and invisible successes, which indicate that it would be worthwhile to resume this partnership with the PDHC, as well as to carry out more training activities in the communities, to work with new pedagogical practices adapted to the current situation, which would undoubtedly strengthen the movement and the rural women of this precious Northeast, the land of our people, where we were born and where we create emotional ties. It would therefore be beneficial for the project and for the movement. ”

Testimony from Margarida Pereira da Silva (75)

who lives in a rural community in the municipality of Casinhas, Pernambuco:

“ My first contact with PDHC was through a networking meeting with various organizations, movements, international cooperation agencies and a project consultant. At this meeting I represented MMTR-NE as the Executive Secretary. At that time, we were discussing the economic situation of the movement, since we were not able to continue our actions due to a lack of resources, especially in relation to the work we were doing with rural women workers to obtain their documents so that they could have access to their rights and public policies. At that time, it was decided that MMTR-NE, in partnership with PDHC I, would implement a project to work on the documentation of rural women in the semiarid of the Northeastern region. In 2002, I was the Executive Secretary of the MMTR-NE, and when the project was approved, I was part of the general coordination.

At that time, in the early 2000s, there were almost no public policies aimed at rural women. But if they didn't have documents, they couldn't take advantage of the few opportunities that were available. Thus, the PDHC enabled MMTR-NE to continue its grassroots work and training, reaching rural women in the most diverse communities in the Northeast, which had not been possible before due to lack of resources. Therefore, the partnership with the PDHC was essential for women to have access to their documents and public policies, including PRONAF Mulher.

Seeing the happiness on the faces of each of the rural women workers when they accessed their documents made us very happy. In fact, the documentation campaign had such a great impact that it became public policy through the Federal Government's National Program for the Documentation of Rural Women Workers. We are very proud of our movement for achieving this with the support of the PDHC.

It's important to mention that the work of PDHC I was not only aimed at providing documentation for rural women workers, but also at guaranteeing their citizenship and access to their rights. To this end, the PDHC provided the women with the ATER, using a participatory methodology that made it possible to create a space for learning and sharing experiences. We believe that this support was crucial for the successful development of the project. The technicians followed the whole process very closely, including the training sessions that were held and that dealt with issues that affect our daily lives, such as domestic violence, gender issues, guidance on our rights, the importance of women's participation in leadership positions in organizations and political parties, etc.

As a result, the number of women in social organizations and in decision-making positions increased. In addition, many women joined rural trade unions, which made it possible for them to retire at an old age, since they also had their documents in hand.

In terms of production, after PDHC I, the women began to adopt more sustainable practices and to produce food and medicinal herbs organically. For example, there was a change in the practice of burning leaves and waste. In this case, the women began to reuse the leaves as fertilizer and to separate organic waste (for composting) from recyclable waste (PET bottles were used in the garden beds and plastic bags were reused for handicrafts).

”

The background features a faint, light-colored illustration of a community meeting. Several people are depicted in a circle, some holding papers or maps. In the center, a large map or document is spread out on a table. The overall style is simple and line-art-like, set against a solid orange background.

Dom Hélder Câmara Project II²

² The information and data included in this chapter comes from the PDHC II Completion Report.

From 2014 to 2024, several external events directly influenced the design of the second phase of the Project, such as:

- political changes and economic difficulties;
- the biggest water crisis of the 21st century; and
- the COVID-19 pandemic.

In light of these realities, PDCH II had to be reinvented in order to meet its goals and objectives.

30

Area of operation

The area of operation of PDHC II was expanded to include the Superintendence for the Development of Brazilian Northeast (SUDENE) region of influence, covering a total of 913 municipalities in 11 states. These include:

- **All 9 states of the Northeast region:** Alagoas, Bahia, Ceará, Maranhão, Paraíba, Pernambuco, Piauí, Rio Grande do Norte and Sergipe; and
- **Other 2 states of the Southeast region:** Minas Gerais and Espírito Santo.

PDHC II objective

*The general objective of PDHC II was to contribute to the **reduction of poverty and rural inequality** in the semiarid region BY:*

- enhancing articulation and access to sustainable rural development policies for family farmers in the semiarid region of Brazil; and
- improving the design of public policies for the semiarid region, based on the systematization and replication of innovations and successful experiences that took place during the project.

PDHC participant in Cabaceiras/PB.

PDHC II budget

USD 125 million

were invested to achieve the objective set for the PDHC II, of which:

32

- USD 3 million from IFAD
- USD 15 million from AECID

Solar panels for the agricultural sanitation and reuse system.

ATER in the PDHC II

In order to adapt to the institutional changes in the Federal Government, the method of contracting ATER services had to be changed from the previous phase of the Project. In PDHC II, the MDA entered into a management contract with the National Agency for Technical Assistance and Rural Extension (ANATER), which became responsible for contracting and managing the provision of ATER services. ANATER contracted public and private ATER companies through a specific partnership instrument and public tenders to provide services for an average of two years.

The strategic alliance with ANATER participating

57,933 families

through the services provided by 17 companies in the private sector and 10 in the public sector. In this case, the actions involved: training, support for the implementation of agro-ecological practices, diversification of production systems aimed at family self-consumption and the sale of surpluses.

Among the families assisted by ATER services:

- **16,040** benefited from the Rural Productive Activities Promotion Program (or Rural Development Program) of the Ministry of Social Development and Fight Against Hunger (MDS) in the amount of BRL 2,400.00 per family; and
- **2,394 families** from quilombola communities benefited from the Rural Development Program in the amount of BRL 4,600.00 per family.

PROGRAMA FOMENTO RURAL

34

The Rural Development Program, established by Law No. 12,512 of 14/10/2011 and regulated by Decree No. 9,221 of 06/12/2017, and its amendments, combines income transfer with social and productive monitoring through the design and implementation of productive development projects.

Under PDHC II there was coordination between

The objective was to **promote the productive integration of family farmers** living in extreme poverty, so that they could increase their production for both their self-consumption and the sale of their surplus, thereby increasing their income.

Other PDHC II actions and partnerships

PDHC II actions were carried out in collaboration with a wide range of partnerships. Thus, in addition to the provision of ATER services, other actions were carried out through decentralized execution terms (TEDs) with federal public institutions. Partnership agreements were signed with

12 institutions.

In a Project as comprehensive as PDHC II, the articulation and formation of partnerships was a strategic factor in the implementation of activities and the achievement of objectives.

- **9 partner institutions** worked **directly with families**, family farming organizations, and traditional peoples and communities (PCTs), providing training and addressing issues such as technological innovations that are relevant and necessary for family farmers in the semi-arid region;
- **1 partnership** was established with the **National Institute of Colonization and Agrarian Reform (INCRA)** through the Secretariat for Rural Women of the MDA. The aim of this partnership was to carry out joint efforts to document rural women workers in the semi-arid region; and
- **2 partnerships** were established with **universities** to assist with the Project's evaluation activities.

Benefiting a total of

12,370 families

14,719 people

were assisted

35

The UNB carried out the impact evaluation and monitoring of ATER services.

The UFV evaluated the results of the TEDs.

In summary, the total number of families benefited and the actions carried out by the other partnerships formalized through TEDs were as follows:

1,000

families have benefited from actions carried out under the TED signed with FINEP/FNDCT.

- These actions included the rescue of traditional cheese-making technologies to enhance biological, social and cultural diversity, and the dissemination of good practices in the production and processing of milk and dairy products.

65

families benefited from the activities carried out in the TED signed with CODEVASF..

- This institution was responsible for the production and distribution of cochineal-resistant fodder palm seedlings.

1,822

families benefited from the actions carried out under the TED signed with IF Sertão

- The actions were related to the transfer of knowledge, technologies, processes, products and services to overcome the main challenges of sheep production in the São Francisco production area, in the hinterlands of Pernambuco.

1,490

families benefited from the actions carried out under the TED signed with INSA.

- The focus of the actions was the diffusion of the cultivation of cochineal-resistant fodder palm, through the installation of production units using water reuse for local irrigation, by means of production cisterns linked to photovoltaic energy systems. In this scenario, the dissemination of Environmental Sanitation and Water Reuse (SARA) deserves to be highlighted.

PDHC II participation in the Semiarid Show.

SARA (Environmental Sanitation and Water Reuse) water reuse system, through the National Semiarid Institute (INSA).

Diversification of products derived from jaboticaba and multiplication of creole seeds at the Mixed Cooperative of Peasant Production and Commercialization of Alagoas - COOPCAM, in the municipality of Palmeira dos Índios/AL, supported by PDHC II through Embrapa Foods and Territories.

Seedling nursery of the Association of Alternative Farmers - AAGRA in Igaci/AL, supported by PDHC II, through Embrapa Foods and Territories.

The actions carried out under the TEDs signed with each of the decentralized units of the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (Embrapa) and the number of families served:

* Two different TEDs were implemented at the same Embrapa unit.

Embrapa Semiárid*

Training for extension workers and farming families in technologies for the coexistence with the semiárid, which covered the following topics: agro-industrial use of native fruit; keeping stingless bees; production of seeds and seedlings from the Caatinga; grey-water reuse; composting and use of waste.

469
families assisted

It supported the participation of the families assisted by the Project in a technology fair for the semiárid region (the Semiárido Show, the largest fair in the Brazilian semiárid region).

No direct participating subjects in the Project³.

* Two different TEDs were implemented at the same Embrapa unit.

³ The funds were used to set up the structure of the technology fair, which attracted thousands of visitors. Therefore, there were no direct participating subjects.

Embrapa Mid-North

Training for ATER technicians and women in the Mid-North region of Brazil on production activities related to cowpea, beekeeping, sheep and goat breeding, free-range chickens and the Embrapa's Sisteminha.

886
families assisted

Partnerships with Embrapa's decentralized units located in the Northeast were very important for the effectiveness of PDHC II actions, as they allowed the introduction of technological innovations and the production of materials to disseminate best practices on topics of priority to the Project's participating subjects.

Impacts of PDHC II

The impact evaluation of PDCH II estimated:

- a reduction of approximately **90% in extreme poverty** among beneficiaries of ATER services;
- an increase of **23% in the assets of participating families**; and
- an impact on the variability of household income through the improvement of agricultural income (animal and plant production) of up to
 - **16% for families who have not participate in the Rural Development Program**; and
 - **30% for those who participated.**

Therefore, the PDHC II promoted:

reduction of rural poverty and increase in income!

In addition, the Project generated other positive impacts by enabling:

THE STRENGTHENING OF HUMAN AND SOCIAL CAPITAL

Through the training of technicians, the encouragement of the participation of young people and women, training on various topics, actions to promote associations, among others.

THE ACCESS TO SOCIAL TECHNOLOGIES

Some examples of social technologies disseminated in PDHC II were: the Environmental Sanitation and Water Reuse (SARA) technology combined with the distribution of more resistant fodder palm seedlings, genetic improvement of goats, among others.

THE INCREASE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY

Through increased agricultural production, the efficient use of appropriate inputs, access to technological innovations and the adoption of good production practices.

THE ACCESS TO MARKETS

In particular, sales at fairs and institutional markets.

THE IMPROVEMENT OF NUTRITION AND FOOD SECURITY

By increasing the availability of and access to food.

Other key indicators from the PDHC II impact evaluation showed that the objectives were not only met, but exceeded during this phase. For example:

42

53,483

families reported adopting new/improved inputs, technologies or practices.

This figure represents 297% of the initial goal!

16,790

families reported an increase in production, or 104% of the initial goal of 16,154 families.

This figure represents 104% of the initial goal!

2,592

ATER agents were trained, 549 of whom were women.

These figures exceed the initial goals of 250 and 125, respectively.

89

Knowledge Management (KM) products have been created (54 videos and 35 booklets).

In total
70,303
families

participated in
PDHC II

57,933

FAMILIES BENEFITED FROM ATER ACTIONS

In some cases, there was a combination of ATER and the Rural Development Program, which enabled the financing of productive projects for a portion of the families. In addition, various ATER providers monitored approximately 1,300 reference units, with the objective of optimizing and multiplying successful experiences among participating subjects.

12,370

FAMILIES PARTICIPATED IN TEDs INITIATIVES

This modality was also an innovation compared to traditional ATER services, as it brings public research institutions closer to family farmers. This interaction led to the:

**Identification of new
research demands**

**the availability of technological innovations and
access to knowledge within the family, as well as
in productive and commercial social organizations
such as cooperatives and associations.**

In general, farming families were given the opportunity to upgrade their existing food production (farming and/or animal husbandry adapted to the semiarid region), which enabled:

- the maintenance of cultural heritage;
- the increase of women's autonomy; and
- the resilience in the face of challenging conditions.

Rural women

With the aim of contributing to greater gender equality and women's autonomy in rural areas, rural women were one of the priority groups served by PDHC II.

To this end, the Project has developed an action strategy that has achieved important results with women. In particular, the Project:

44

45,393 women benefited

from PDHC II. Approximately 23,000 women received ATER services without participating in the Rural Development Program, in addition to 5,500 who received support through the initiatives implemented through the TEDs.

Ensured the inclusion of women in productive activities, taking into account their specific demands and needs.

Provided the opportunity to develop women's capacities through the access to ATER services, enabling them to value their role in family production and to improve their performance through training.

Increased women's economic autonomy through access to and control over resources from the Rural Development Program. For example, out of a total of 18,434 benefits, 77% were granted to women.

Helped women to be socially recognized in the families' economic-productive sphere through the use of Agroecological Logbooks.

Preparing the field for the Caupi bean production course, organized by EMBRAPA Mid-North.

Rural workers' documentation task force through INCRA.

Jams and jellies, Gameleiras, Desterro, Bahia, through EMBRAPA Semiárid.

Delivery of fodder palm rackets by CODEVASF.

Field of fodder palm irrigated with reused water, through actions of the National Semiárid Institute (INSA).

Rural youth

Rural youth was another priority public in PDHC II and all the actions developed were aimed at integrating this public. The main results are:

INCREASED ECONOMIC AUTONOMY by helping young people accessing resources, assets and services. In general, this makes it possible for young people to:

- increase food production; and
- make a positive impact in their communities by increasing participation in rural Community organization, for example.

10,698 young people

between the ages of 15 and 29 who are responsible for some kind of productive activity were supported by PDHC II through ATER providers. Of this total,

3,418
are young
men

**13% of these
young men
participated
in the Rural
Development
Program**

7,280
are young women

**31% of these young women
participated in the Rural
Development Program**

Traditional peoples and communities

Under PDHC II, the PCTs were also part of the priority public. These are the main results:

6,119

families from quilombola communities benefited from the Project, of which

75% participated in the Rural Development Program.

345

families from indigenous communities benefited from PDHC II. Of which:

54% participated in the Rural Development Program.

47

The Quilombola ATER Program in PDHC II

In addition, for the first time there was a call for ATER providers that focused exclusively family farmers from rural quilombola communities certified by the Palmares Cultural Foundation. The purpose of this program was to expand the range of ATER services offered and the possibilities of access to rural public policies for this population.

3,200

families from quilombola communities were assisted by the Quilombola ATER. Of which:

74,8%

participated in the Rural Development Program

After 24 years
of history, a
new phase is
beginning:
PDHC III

PROJETO
DOM
HÉLDER
CÂMARA

Dom Hélder

Câmara Project III

Background

Despite the significant results and positive impacts achieved through the implementation of the two phases of the PDHC, the socio-economic reality of family farming in the Brazilian semiarid remains the same:

**high levels
of poverty**

**nutrition and food
insecurity**

50

These problems, together with the worsening of climate change and its impact on the semiarid region, create extremely challenging and priority demands for government action.

Influenced by this context, the Secretariat for Land Governance, Territorial and Socio-Environmental Development (SFDT/MDA) began negotiations with IFAD in 2023 to design the third phase of the PDHC. In particular, this design involved an extensive process of dialogue with public institutions and social movements, which resulted in **the launch of PDHC III in December 2024, to be implemented by 2030.**

PDHC III launch event in December 2024, Brasília/DF.

PDHC III components and Corresponding actions

Interventions to operationalize the objectives of PDHC III will be carried out
through 3 components:

1°

Promoting Nutrition and Food Security from an Agroecological Perspective

Improving family income and nutrition and food security by strengthening the productive capacity of family farmers. In addition, the aim is to strengthen family farming organizations so that they are able to absorb surplus production, process it and market it with added value.

This component will work on:

- resilient and diversified agroecological production;
- strengthening market access capacities; and
- virtual technical assistance (VTA).

2°

Capacity Building, Innovation and Knowledge Dissemination

Improve and update the knowledge and skills of the Project's professionals (such as the extension and technical assistance teams), as well as some of the participating subjects, to promote agroecological transition and sustainable and nutritious agri-food systems.

This component will work on:

- innovation and capacity building;
- strengthening young people's capacities; and
- knowledge management, South-South and Triangular Cooperation (SSTC) and policy dialog.

3°

Project Management and Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E)

All necessary project management activities to ensure efficient implementation will be carried out by a Project Management Unit (PMU) under the responsibility of the SFDT/MDA. In addition, the M&E system will support the planning, monitoring and evaluation of results.

In relation to the **ACTIONS FORE-SEEN** in each of the components:

1°

Promoting Nutrition and Food Security from an Agroecological Perspective

PROVISION OF ATER SERVICES AND OTHER MODALITIES OF TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE, ALLIED WITH THE RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM, WITH AN AGRO-ECOLOGICAL AND COEXISTENCE WITH THE SEMIARID FOCUS, IN ADDITION TO SPECIFIC METHODOLOGIES FOR WOMEN, YOUNG PEOPLE AND PCTs

with a view to producing healthy food, adding value, accessing markets, collective organization and access to public policies. There will be actions aimed at implementing Agroforestry Systems, Embrapa's Sisteminha, productive backyards, among others, as well as virtual technical assistance pilots;

INTEGRATION OF TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE WITH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF WATER ACCESS SYSTEMS

for production and consumption (MDS cisterns and others) and water reuse (such as Bioágua and SARA);

PROVISION OF TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE AND SPECIFIC INVESTMENTS TO COLLECTIVE FAMILY FARMING ORGANIZATIONS

with the aim of strengthening organizational capacities, adding value to products and gaining access to public and private markets, including actions that contribute to access to health certifications and collective trademarks that indicate the origin of family farm products/services, PCTs and indigenous peoples;

SUPPORT FOR FAMILY CENTERS FOR ALTERNANCE TRAINING (CEFFAS)

through scholarships for students and teachers and investment in the development and dissemination of pedagogical content, to act as multipliers of knowledge and good agroecological practices in rural territories, in conjunction with universities and federal institutes; and

IMPLEMENTATION OF A PILOT PROJECT ON VIRTUAL TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE

including studies on existing tools, methods, potentials, limitations and innovations on the subject, in an integrated and complementary way to the irreplaceable dynamics of face-to-face, individual and collective training processes in family farming.

2°

Capacity Building, Innovation and Knowledge Dissemination

PROVISION OF TRAINING PROCESSES

for technical assistance teams, civil society organizations, including family farming associations and cooperatives. The aim is to improve the quality of ATER and the co-construction of knowledge in rural territories.

SUPPORT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF AND ACCESS TO SOCIAL TECHNOLOGIES ADAPTED TO THE SEMIARID

this action includes the implementation of learning/demonstration units, as well as the dissemination of good practices, innovations and lessons learned from the Project.

PLANNING OF TERRITORIAL, REGIONAL, NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL EVENTS; EXCHANGES AND SEMINARS

for the exchange of experiences, the social management of public policies and technological innovation in family farming, as well as the expansion of the participation of civil society in the implementation cycle of public policies for sustainable rural development.

53

3°

Project Management and Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E)

IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND M&E ACTIONS

integrated into collegiate governance bodies at the territorial, regional and national levels, bringing together civil society organizations representing family farming and state governments in the preparation and alignment of actions.

Alignment of PDHC III

with the sustainable development goals

All of PDHC III actions are aligned with achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) from the United Nations' 2030 Agenda.

54

In this case, efforts are focused mainly on the following SDGs:

Focus of actions and the budget for PDHC III

In this new phase, the general focus of PDHC III actions is:

REDUCTION of RURAL POVERTY and GENDER, GENERATIONAL and ETHNIC RACIAL UN-EQUALITIES

STRENGTHENING the RESILIENCE of FAMILY FARMING to the impact of climate change, using the paradigms of AGROECOLOGY and the COEXISTENCE WITH THE SEMIARID as a REFERENCE.

For the implementation of the actions foreseen in PDHC III, the direct budget of SFDT/MDA is approximately,

BRL 221 million.

Of this total:

77,8%

will come from the loan agreement with IFAD.

55

Territorial approach and area of operation

PDHC III is being planned and implemented according to the territorial approach to sustainable rural development, which recognizes **THE RURAL TERRITORY** as the reference unit and seeking to promote social participation and synergy between the subjects of the territories, the integration of public policies and the strengthening of federative articulation. The Project area consists of **30 rural territories from the semi-arid region, located in the 9 states of the Northeast plus Minas Gerais.**

56

The following prioritization criteria were used to define the rural territories:

- Drought risk index (MCTI)
- Concentration of agrarian reform settlements
- Have at least 50% of their municipalities located in the semi-arid region, in accordance with the CONDEL/SUDENE Resolution No. 150/2021
- Food insecurity index (MDS)
- Concentration of family farming establishments
- Concentration of PCTs
- Incidence of poverty (percentage of CadÚnico registrants)

Target audience and access to the project

PDHC III is expected to serve

90,000
family farmers
and their families.

Families, groups and organizations will be prioritized as follows:

Included in these targets is assistance to land reform and land credit settlers, who are also priority audiences for PDHC III.

Participants identification and access to PDHC III will be decentralized through partnerships with:

- public organizations; and
- civil society organizations.

These partners must actively seek out the families, groups and organizations that will benefit from PDHC III, based on the Project's guidelines and targeting criteria, using participatory methods with a territorial focus. The objective is to promote:

- social participation;
- the integration of public policies; and
- the strengthening of federative coordination.

*If you have any questions, criticisms or suggestions, please send us an
e-mail: projetodomheldercamara@mda.gov.br*

